

DISTINGUISHING THREE SPECIES OF MOSSES OF SIMILAR SPECTRAL PROPERTIES IN GALINDEZ ISLAND, MARITIME ANTARCTICA, USING SPECTRAL REFLECTANCE INDICES

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In Maritime Antarctica, vegetation changes rapidly in response to climate change, air temperature increase and altered water availability, respectively. Therefore, poikilohydric mosses can be considered sensitive stress markers of environmental change. Our study focuses on environmentally-driven alterations in their spectral properties.

Spectral reflectance indices for mosses *Warnstorfia fontinaliopsis*, *Chorisodontium aciphyllum* and *Sanionia georgicouncinata* in the Galindez Island (Argentine Islands) were measured in order to find suitable ones for effective moss species classification if they demonstrate the same color state (green).

The study was performed in the summer season of 2023/24 during the XXVIII Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition at Galindez Island. The measurements were carried out on the moss bank Kupol (-65.2481°, -64.2462°). On the surface of the moss bank, 5 uniform green state spots sized 10 × 10 cm were selected for each species studied. The spots were monospecific, homogeneous without being interspersed with other species. 5–10 measurements of reflectance spectra were taken for each spot using a handheld spectrometer PolyPen RP 410 UVIS (Photon Systems Instruments, Drásov, Czech Republic) within the range of 380–790 nm. 19 spectral reflectance indices were calculated using Spectrapen software. Among them, some did not differ significantly between the studied species (e.g., OSAVI). The majority of indices, however, were sensitive enough to distinguish individual studied species. The indices that distinguished *W. fontinaliopsis* green state from other species studied were: NDVI, SR, MCARI, TCARI, PSNDa, ARI1, ARI2 (and ZMI, Ctr2, SIPI, GM1, GM2, CRI1, CRI2). The indices that distinguished *Ch. aciphyllum* green state from other species studied were: SRPI, NPQI, NPCI, Ctr1 (and ZMI, Ctr2, SIPI, GM1, GM2, CRI1, CRI2). The indices that distinguished *S. georgicouncinata* green state from other species studied were: MCARI1, TVI, PRI (and ZMI, Ctr2, SIPI, GM1, GM2, CRI1, CRI2).

Finally, the indices with statistically significant differences for all studied moss species were identified (ZMI, Ctr2, SIPI, GM1, GM2, CRI1, and CRI2) and suggested for follow-up studies.

Moreover, the indices calculated at wavelengths typical for UAV spectral cameras (green, red and red edge channels) showed species-specific differences. Such indices (HSMI, R730/R550, R790/R730, R730/R650) can potentially be used to distinguish between different mosses within the same physiological state indicating a good vigor.